

AIJACLA

Annual International Journal on Analysis of Contemporary Legal Affairs

Vol. 1

January, 2021

About the Journal

An International,
Double-blind,
Peer-reviewed and
Annually published
Journal.

Contact Details

Email:

aequitasvictoria@gmail.com

Helpline Number:

8473808112

Office Address:

H/o Shri Sarthak Aryan,
C/o Shri Subodh Kumar,
Old Madhya Bihar Gramin
Bank Building,
Sakurabad
P.O.: Sakurabad,
Dist: Jehanabad,
PIN: 804425 (Bihar).

Published By

**Aequitas Victoria
Foundation**

www.aequivic.in

AEQUITAS VICTORIA FOUNDATION PRESENTS ANNUAL INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL ON ANALYSIS OF CONTEMPORARY LEGAL AFFAIRS

ABOUT THE JOURNAL

Annual International Journal on Analysis of Contemporary Legal Affairs (AIJACLA) is an annual international double-blind peer-reviewed journal in the field of law. The journal deals with contemporary affairs primarily within the discipline of law but also encourages interdisciplinary research works from any discipline provided the relation of the subject-matter with the legal institutions, legal instruments, or any other legal matters shall be established and highlighted to meet the eligibility criteria of the journal.

Broadly the Journal welcomes research works from each branch of law like: Human Rights, Humanitarian Rights, IPR, Environmental Law, Public and Private International Law, Air and Space Law, Drone Law, Martial Law, Sports Law, Fashion Law, etc. It even encourages contributions from panel discussion or conference reports based on the topics of recent developments in the field of law. Further, case commentaries, law book reviews, legislative and policy analysis are also welcomed. The journal will also publish contributions that are not expressly from the discipline of law but establishes a relation with any of the legal matters and gives it an interdisciplinary character.

However, comments regarding decisions pending before any Court of Law or any other subject matter across the globe which if published might lead to Contempt of Court, if interpreted from the perspective of Indian Jurisprudence, will not be published even if the matter does not violate any of the Indian Laws or does not amount to any offense in any other laws.

SCOPE

The scope of this journal extends to the entire world transcending all national boundaries of the States. It is an international journal aimed at establishing a global network of research and analysis in the field of law. The medium of publication will be primarily **American English** subject to the majority opinion of the Board of Editors, Expert Committee, and the Board of Advisors in conformity with the Core Team including the Managing Committee.

The Journal is expected to be a globally open accessed journal subject to the technical limitations and international or regional laws in force or existence anywhere either internationally or nationally.

The journal intends to cover all fields of law including-

1. International Conventions passed by International or Global Bodies;
2. Regional Conventions, Rules, Policies, etc. passed by Regional Organizations that are recognized globally;
3. Rules, Policies, By-laws, etc. passed by any Inter-state bodies provided such matters influence the relationship between two or more countries that are recognized as sovereign under the international rules;
4. Any other Conventions, Laws, Rules, etc. that are not directly recognized by any international or global bodies or agencies but are going to influence or has an impact on the diplomatic relationships between two or more countries;
5. Cases decided by International Adjudicating Authorities;
6. Any Laws, By-laws, Enactments, Policies, etc. passed by a proper legislative authority, competent courts, authorities with proper legal recognitions in any sovereign country;
7. Conference, Seminar, Colloquium, etc. reports that are based on topics of law;
8. Lectures from eminent professionals in the field of law, or lectures on legal topics from eminent personalities;
9. Researches made on Theories relevant to the field of Law;
10. Any researchable topic from any discipline provided the subject-matter of such research shall properly establish the nexus with the legal institutions, instruments, or any other subject-matter of law; and
11. Results of researches carried out independently either as an individual, group, or as an organization in the field of law.

However, the journal shall not publish any material related to the following either in whole or in part subject to the approval of the Board of Editors, Expert Committee, Board of Advisors in conformity with the Core Team including the Managing Committee-

1. Comments regarding decisions pending before any Court of Law or any other subject matter across the globe which if published might lead to Contempt of Court, if interpreted from the perspective of Indian Jurisprudence, will not be published even if the matter does not violate any of the Indian Laws or does not amount to any offense in any other laws;
2. Political opinions even if based on legal topics that are suspected of influencing voting behavior of the citizens of any sovereign country against the provisions of an established legislations either international, regional, or local, or is expected to incite rebellion or conflict against any popularly established government; provided such materials may be published considering the authenticity of the sources, the justification of the author(s), the need and demand of the time or situation and above all the decision of the Board of Editors, Expert Committee, Board of Advisors in conformity with the Core Team along with the Managing Committee;
3. Any discriminatory opinions regarding racial, gender, or any other class of people, or comments in favor of any particular group, institution, organization, party, community, etc.; provided such materials may be published considering the authenticity of the sources, the justification of the author(s), the need and demand of the time or situation and above all the decision of the Board of Editors, Expert Committee, Board of Advisors in conformity with the Core Team along with the Managing Committee; or
4. Any other immoral, offensive, comments, or comments against any established custom or culture.

OBJECTIVES

1. To provide a platform for Indian Legal Professionals including Judges, Academicians, Advocates, and Students for showcasing their research skills;
2. To build an endeavor of research and analytical altitude amongst the young legal professionals under the experience and guidance of the senior legal experts;
3. To highlight the possible developments needed in the area of law through research and analytical spirits;
4. To encourage the habit of critical analysis and argumentative behavior amongst the law students; and
5. To help in policy formulation and legal drafting in India by expressing suggestions brought forward through research skills.

BOARD OF EDITORS

Editor-in-Chief

Prof. (Dr) Chintamani Rout

HOD. Department of Law
North-Eastern Hill University, Shillong

Senior Editor

Prof. (Dr) Yugal Kishore

Professor of Law, ICFAI Law School,
ICFAI University Dehradun, Former
Professor, Registrar, Vice-Chancellor
National Law University and Judicial
Academy Assam

Senior Editor

Dr. Heru Susetyo

Assistant professor, Faculty of Law,
Universitas Indonesia, Jakarta,
Indonesia.

Chairman of the Center for Islam and
Islamic Law, Faculty of Law,
Universitas Indonesia, Jakarta,
Indonesia.

Senior Editor

Mrs. Ronaldah Lerato Karabo Ozah

Director- Litigation, Research and
Advocacy and Lecturer, Centre for
Child Law, University of Pretoria, South
Africa.

Senior Editor

Dr Dhrubajyoti Das

Associate Professor, Department of
English, Cotton University

Senior Editor

Dr. Sachin Ghimire

Medical Anthropologist and Filmmaker
Assistant professor, Department of
Public health, Manamohan Memorial
Institute of Health Sciences(MMIHS),
Kathmandu, Nepal.

Senior Editor

Senior Editor

Senior Editor

Dr. Matiur Rahman

Assistant Professor, University Law
College Gauhati University

Associate Editors

Mr. Animesh Jha

Assistant Professor, Dharmashastra
National Law University, Jodhpur

Associate Editors

Ms. Moushita Dutta

LLM, McGill University, Montreal,
Canada.

Mrs. Mageswary Siva Subramaniam

Lecturer with Faculty of Law,
Multimedia University (Malacca
Campus), Malacca, Malaysia.
Visiting lecturer, Lingnan University,
Hong Kong

Associate Editors

Mr. Animesh Jha

Assistant Professor, Family Law,
Dharmashastra National Law University
(DNLU), Jabalpur.

Mrs. Rima Borthakur

Former Senior Manager, Document
Review department in Thomson Reuters
(Pangea3), New York City.

Associate Editors

Mr. Prithvi Raaj Choudhury

LLM, McGill University, Montreal,
Canada.

Associate Editors

Mr. Amey Pandey

Co-Founder CLAT Junction, Working
with Safe in India Foundation

EXPERT COMMITTEE

**Prof (Dr) Bhaskar Kumar
Chakravarty**

Visiting Professor of Law Royal Global
University, Former Professor Dean and
Head Department of Law, Gauhati
University, Founder Head of
Department of Law, Tezpur University

Dr Gautami Dutta

Principal R.K.B. Law College

Dr Anup Kumar Ray

Principal, Goalpara Law College

Prof (Dr) Atul Chandra Talukdar

Dean School of Social Science &
Humanities, University of Science &
Technology Meghalaya

Dr Ajay Kumar Das

Principal, Jorhat Law College

Dr Md. Sultan Haidar Alam

Principal NERIM Law College

Dr Kasturi Gakul

Assistant Professor of Law
National Law University and Judicial
Academy Assam

Dr Bimal Kumar Baishya

Associate Professor (Rtd.), University
Law College Gauhati University

Dr Sujata Bhattacharyya

Principal Nowgong Law College

Advocate Dr Lalan Prasad Thakuria

Editor Nyaijyoti, All Assam Lawyers
Association

REVIEW COMMITTEE

Mrs. Dimpy Saikia

Assistant Professor, Nowgong Law
College

Designation: Member Content
Assessment Committee

Rashmi Gogoi

Research Scholar Gauhati University
Designation: Member Content
Assessment Committee

Mrs. Karishma Saikia

Assistant Professor, Nowgong Law
College

Designation: Member Content
Assessment Committee

Darshana Deepak Das

MA in English Litt (Specialization in
Indian Literature), PGT in Potential and
Concept Academy, Working as an SME
in AMF Edu Solutions
Designation: Member Content

Suyash Pranay Tripathi

PGDCPLP, National Law School of
India University Bangalore, LLM
National Law University, Odisha
Designation: Member Content
Assessment Committee

Anya Behera

LLM from National Law University and
Judicial Academy Assam, LLB from
KIT School of Law Bhubaneswar
Designation: Member Content
Assessment Committee

Rashi Gupta

LLM National Law University and
Judicial Academy Assam, LLB
Vivekananda Institute of Professional
Studies, New Delhi
Designation: Member Content
Assessment Committee

Alekh

LLM, National Law University and
Judicial Academy Assam, LLB KIT
Law School Bhubaneswar
Designation: Member Content
Assessment Committee

Srishti

Student at Chanakya National Law
University, Bihar
Aadya Ambastha
Student at Chanakya National Law
University, Bihar
Designation: Format Assessment
Committee

Ishan Mishra

Student
ICFAI Law College, Dehradun
Designation: Format Assessment
Committee

Assessment Committee

Girisha Sinha

LLM National Law University and
Judicial Academy Assam, LLB KIT
Law School Bhubaneswar
Designation: Member Content
Assessment Committee

Prachi Prem

Student at Chanakya National Law
University, Bihar
Designation: Format Assessment
Committee

Monalisa Choudhury

Student at National Law University,
Assam
Ishan Mishra
Student at ICFAI University Dehradun
Designation: Format Assessment
Committee

Pranay Rathore

Student at Fairfield Institute of
Management and Technology, New
Delhi
Designation: Member Plagiarism and
Ethics Review Committee

Riya Kumari

Student at University Law College,
Hazaribagh
Designation: Member Plagiarism and
Ethics Review Committee

Shreya Gupta

Student at JIMS Engineering
Management Technical Campus, Noida
Designation: Member Plagiarism and
Ethics Review Committee

Prachi Nayan

LLM National Law University and
Judicial Academy Assam, LLB, ICFAI
Law School, Dehradun
Designation: Member Content
Assessment Committee

Saloni Sharma

Student at Fairfield Institute of
Management and Technology, New
Delhi
Designation: Format Assessment
Committee

Bomkesh Mandal

Student at National Law University,
Assam
Riya Sharma
Student at Fairfield Institute of
Management and Technology, New
Delhi
Designation: Format Assessment
Committee

Basuri Poddar

Student at National Law University and
Judicial Academy Assam
Designation: Member Plagiarism and
Ethics Review Committee

CORE TEAM (MANAGING COMMITTEE)

Mrs Nidhi Tiwari

Hon'ble Secretary

Ms Vidisha Dixit

Hon'ble Member

Mrs Pranati Boruah

Hon'ble President

Mr Subodh Kumar

Hon'ble Treasurer

Mr Jayanta Boruah

Hon'ble Member (Founder)

Mr Manik Chandra Boruah

Hon'ble Member

Mr Sarthak Aryan

Hon'ble Member (Co-Founder)

ADMINISTRATIVE SECTION

Executive Committee

Chief Executive Officer

Ms Kashmiri Khanam

Assistant Professor, Dhubri Law
College, Research Scholar, Central
University of Haryana

Executive Officer

Ms Saloni Sharma

Fairfield Institute of Management and
Technology, New Delhi
Executive Officer

Ms Darshee Madhukallya

National Law University and Judicial
Academy Assam

Content Designer

Ms Abhishree Kashay

National Law University and Judicial
Academy Assam

Event Manager

Ms Basnuri Poddar

National Law University and Judicial
Academy Assam

Executive Officer

Ms Gautami Chakravarty

KIT School of Law Bhubaneswar

Executive Officer

Ms Riya Kumari

University Law College, Hazaribagh

Content designer

Bonaini Deori

Advocate, Gauhati High Court

Content Designer

Ms Nijhum Roy

National Law University and Judicial
Academy Assam

Event Manager

Ms Puja Bardhan

West Guwahati Commerce College

Event Manager

Ms Nargis Choudhury

Former Lecturer, School of Law and
Judicial Sciences, Apex Professional
University, Arunachal Pradesh

Executive Officer

Mr Chetan Anand Mahapatra

National Law University and Judicial
Academy Assam

Executive Officer

Ms Shreya Gupta

JIS Engineering Management Technical
Campus, Noida

Content Designer

Ms Dikshita Nanda Nath

Advocate, Gauhati High Court

Content Designer

Mr Arunabh Chakravarty

Department of English, Gauhati
University

Event Manager

Mr Debanjan Das

National Law University and Judicial
Academy Assam

Disciplinary Committee

Chairman

Mr Manik Chandra Boruah

Rtd. Police Officer, Assam Police
Hon'ble Member Managing Committee,
Aequitas Victoria Foundation

Mrs Nidhi Tiwari

Hon'ble Secretary, The Managing
Committee, Aequitas Victoria
Foundation

Mr Jayanta Boruah

Former Assistant Professor NERIM
Law College, Advocate Gauhati High
Court and Research Scholar North-
Eastern Hill University, Hon'ble
Member The Managing Committee
Aequitas Victoria Foundation

Mr Subodh Kumar

Hon'ble Treasurer, The Managing
Committee, Aequitas Victoria
Foundation

Advocate Rajendra Singh

Suryavanshi

Advocate, Supreme Court of India

Grievance Redressal Committee

Chairman

Dr Matiur Rahman

Assistant Professor
University Law College Gauhati
University

Dr Ajoy Kumar Das

Principal, Jorhat Law College

Advocate Dr Lalan Prasad Thakuria

Member, All Assam Lawyers
Association

Mrs Roseleen Deori

Assistant Professor
Nowgaong Law College

VOLUME 1
(Editorial Special Issue)
2020

AJACLA

Ms Vidisha Dixit
Hon'ble Member The Managing
Committee Aequitas Victoria
Foundation

Media Cell

Mrs Kangkana Goswami
Assistant Editor NE News

Mr Sandeep Deo
Founder, India Speaks Daily
Mrs Prity Deka
Assistant Manager, Axis Bank

Mr Bishaldeep Kakoti
Founder, The Youths Mind

IT Section

Ishita Gupta

United College of Engineering and
Research, Prayagraj

Mr Sarthak Aryan

National Law University and Judicial
Academy Assam, Hon'ble Member The
Managing Committee Aequitas Victoria
Foundation

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Sl No.	Title of Papers and Names and Designations of Authors	Page No.
SECTION A: RESEARCH PAPERS		
1	Affirmative Principle: Making, Breaking and Shaking (MBS) Approach of Judiciary <i>-Dr Rangswami D, Assistant Professor of Law, Karnataka State Law University, Hubballi, Karnataka</i>	1 - 17
2	Clinical and Continuing Legal Education- Interface for Confidence Building Between Law Students and Legal Professionals in Contemporary India <i>- Dr. Md. Sultan Haidar Alam, Principal, NERIM Law College</i>	18 - 29
3	A Critical Appraisal of the Legal Service Authorities Act with Special Reference to Lok Adalat <i>- Dr. Dhiraj Bhusan Sarmah, Former Faculty of Law, University Law College, Gauhati University & Dr. Plabita Saikia, Advocate, Gauhati High Court</i>	30 - 49
4	Establishment of DNA Data Bank in India: A Legal Analysis <i>- Dr. Ranjit Sil, Assistant Professor, Department Of Law, North-Eastern Hill University, Shillong</i>	50 - 64
5	Ecocentric Approaches of the Restorative Justice Theory Vis-à-vis the Legal Issues of Civil and Criminal Liability of the Baghjan Blowout Case in Assam <i>- Dr. Matiur Rahman, Assistant Professor of Law, University Law College, Gauhati University</i>	65 - 76
6	A Comparative Study on Secondary Patenting on Pharmaceutical: Striking A Balance Between Competition Law and IPR <i>- Dr. Kakumani Katakya, Faculty of Law Gauhati University</i>	77 - 90
7	Community and Environmental Protection- - In Search of the Lost Spring of Happiness of the North-Eastern Region <i>- Dr. Sujata Bhattacharyya, Principal, Nowgong Law College</i>	91 - 106
8	National Emergency: A Comparative Analysis of Emergency Laws in India USA and Germany <i>- Abhishek Kumar Khaund, Advocate. Gauhati High Court</i>	107 - 124
9	Legal Frameworks Relating to Use of Pesticides on Horticultural Activities Vis-à-vis Climate Change <i>- Bonani Deori, Advocate, Gauhati High Court & Mritunjoy Barman, Advocate, Gauhati High Court</i>	125 -145
20	The Arms Act, 1959: A Legal Analysis and Comparative Study with USA <i>- Bikash Sen Deka, Advocate, Gauhati High Court</i>	146 -168
11	Comparative Study on Intergovernmental Tax Immunities under the Federal Constitutions of Australia, Canada, India and USA <i>- Bandita Das, Advocate, Gauhati High Court</i>	169 - 177
12	Unlawful Activities and Prevention Act: Balancing National Security with Citizen's Rights <i>- Girisha Sinha, Research Assistant under Advocate Ritesh Kumar Patna High Court</i>	178 - 191
13	An Analysis of the Legal Framework of the Co-operative Banks in India	192 - 215

	- Bidikha Gogoi, Advocate, Gauhati High Court	
14	Parole- The Reformative Instrument of Punishment in Prisonization	216 -228
	- Nayana Medhi, Former Faculty of Law, Indraprastha University	
15	Assam Police and Its Organizational Structure	229 - 271
	- Dr. Anup Kr. Ray, Principal, Goalpara Law College	
SECTION B: ARTICLES		
16	Anti-Defection Law: A Conflict Between the Right to Dissent and the Integrity of the Political Party	273 - 281
	- Apurva Mehta, B.A. LL.B. (Criminal Law Hons.), 5th Year, National University of Study and Research in Law, Ranchi	
17	Contempt of Court: An Urgent Requisite to Re-Explore	282 - 287
	- Paras Gupta, B.A.LL.B.(Hons.), Institute of Law, Kurukshetra University	
18	Lack of Uniform Code of Conduct to Address the Judges in India	288 - 294
	- Saloni Sharma, 3rd Year B.B.A.LL.B, Fairfield Institute of Management and Technology & Riya Sharma, 3rd Year B.B.A.LL.B, Fairfield Institute of Management and Technology	
19	Rejuvenating the Right to Equality and Life under the Paradigm of Transformative Constitution	295 - 301
	- Dr. Daisy Changmai, Faculty of Law, National Law University and Judicial Academy Assam, Former Principal of Dibrugarh Hanumanbux Surojmal Kanoi Law College	
20	Genital Mutilation- An Appeal for Legislative Response in India to Outlaw the Menace	302 - 311
	- Dr. Karavi Barman, Assistant Professor, N.E.F Law College, Guwahati	
21	Surrogacy in India: A Legal Perspective	312 - 319
	- Dr. Shrutimala Goswami, Assistant Professor, NERIM Law College & Arunav Barua., Research Scholar, Assam Don Bosco University	
22	Merger and Amalgamation of Companies in India: AN Analysis of Its Impact on Various Stakeholders	320 - 330
	- Purbaja Sarmah, Advocate, Gauhati High Court	
23	Human Rights Crisis amongst IDPs in Assam: Issues and Challenges	331 - 337
	- Dr. Gautami Dutta, Principal, Dr. R.K.B. Law College, Dibrugarh	
24	Protective Discrimination under the Constitution of India	338 -345
	- Pallabi Nath, LL.M 1 st Semester, Tezpur University	
25	Mob Lynching as a New Offence Emerging in India: A Study with a Special Reference to Assam	346 - 355
	- Nargis Choudhury, Former Faculty of Legal Studies, School of Law and Juridical Sciences Apex Professional University, Pasighat, Arunachal Pradesh	
26	The Doctrine of Pious Obligation and Its Relevance under the Hindu Law in the Present Time	356 - 363
	-Titikhya Barkataki, LL.M, 1st Semester, Gauhati University	
27	COVID-19 Pandemic: Justice Demands for Increasing Deterrence in India	364 - 370

- Jayanta Boruah, Research Scholar, North-Eastern Hill University, Former Assistant Professor of Law & Advocate & Sarthak Aryan, BALLB (3rd Year) National Law University and Judicial Academy Assam

SECTION C: LEGAL ESSAYS

- 28 **Traditional Ecological Knowledge and Biological Diversity Act, 2002: A Critical Analysis** 371 - 378
- Dr. Ravi Kanta Mishra, Assistant Professor, Department of Law, North-Eastern Hill University
- 29 **Trial by Media: A Hindrance in the Path of Justice and Fairness** 379 - 384
- Bidisha Barman, Advocate, Gauhati High Court & Kaustabh Moni Sarma, Advocate, Gauhati High Court
- 30 **Payment of Rent in Commercial Lease Contracts in Context of the COVID Crisis** 385 -391
- Clarissa D'Lima, Student Kirit P. Mehta School of Law, NMIMS Deemed-to-be University, Mumbai
- 31 **Adultery was Never a Crime: It is a Moral Wrong** 392 - 397
- Aadarsh Kumar Shrivastava, B.A.LL.B. 10th semester, Government New Law College Indore MP
- 32 **The Legal Protection for Consumers in Conducting E-Commerce Activities in India** 398 - 403
- Dikshita Nanda, Advocate, Gauhati High Court
- 33 **"Rarest of Rare Case"- Capital Punishment** 404 - 408
- Devika Warriar, Bharata Mata School of Legal Studies, Kerala
- 34 **Mob Lynching in India: A Threat to Mankind** 409 -413
- Nabanita Baruah, Student (BALLB 7th Sem), Department of Law, NERIM Law College
- 35 **Biomedical Waste Management during COVID-19 Pandemic in India** 414 - 418
- Farzin Naz, Advocate, Gauhati High Court
- 36 **Impact of Lockdown on Migrant Workers whether a Humanitarian or Human Rights Crisis?** 419 - 426
- Nikhil Moitra, Student, National Law University and Judicial Academy Assam
- 37 **Right to Privacy and Data Protection Law in India with a Brief Comparative Analysis with UK and USA** 427 - 433
- Bandana Saikia, Student, Symbiosis Law School Pune
- 38 **Rise of Pedophiles amidst Coronavirus Outbreak** 434 - 440
- Bulbul Kumari, Student, Dharmashastra National Law University, Jabalpur
- 39 **Arrest of Tax Evaders under the Central Goods and Service Tax Act 2017** 441 - 446
- Hunseng Tungkhang, Student, NERIM Law College

SECTION D: CASE COMMENTARY

- 40 **M/S. Nandhini Deluxe v. M/S. Karnataka Cooperative Milk Producers Federation Ltd** 447 - 454
- Natesh Kumar, B.COM; LL.B.(HONS.), School of Law, SASTRA Deemed University
- 41 **The Interpretation of the Law of Limitation by the Indian Supreme Court during the COVID-19 Pandemic** 455 - 457
- Dr. Smarita Mohanty, Member, State Consumer Disputes Redressal Commission, Odisha
- 42 **Vineeta Sharma v. Rakesh Sharma** 458 - 460

	- <i>Namrata Chakrabarty, Advocate, Gauhati High Court</i>	
43	Dunlop Pneumatic Tyre Co. Ltd. V. Selfridge & Co. Ltd.	461 - 463
	- <i>Chetna Priyam, BA LLB (Hons.), ICFAI University, Dehradun</i>	
44	Anuradha Bhasin v. Union of India	464 - 467
	- <i>Sristi Ray, Student, National Law University and Judicial Academy Assam & Kanika Chugh, Student, National Law University and Judicial Academy Assam</i>	
45	Ashok Kumar Kalra v. Surendra Agnihotori (SLP No. 23599 of 2018)	468 - 470
	- <i>Monalisa Choudhury, Student, National Law University and Judicial Academy Assam</i>	
46	Committee of Creditors Essar Steel India Limited Through Authorized Signatory v. Satish Kumar Gupta and Ors.	471 - 475
	- <i>Rajat Gupta, Student, National Law University and Judicial Academy Assam & Vaishnavi Pandey, Student, National Law University and Judicial Academy Assam</i>	
SECTION E: LEGISLATIVE ANALYSIS		
47	Relevance of Narcotics Drugs and Psychotropic Substances (NDPs) Act, 1985	476 - 480
	- <i>Shivangi Pandey, LL.B.(CONST. LAW SPZ.) (5th Year), University of Petroleum & Energy Studies, Dehradun</i>	
48	Analysis of the Assisted Reproductive Technology (Regulation) Bill, 2020	481 - 485
	- <i>Masia Baruah, Student BALLB 6th Semester, NERIM Law College</i>	
SECTION F: BOOK REVIEW		
49	Just Mercy: A Story of Justice and Redemption	486 - 487
	- <i>Aniket Jadhav, Student, Government Law College, Mumbai</i>	
50	Book Review on Judiciary, Judges and Administration of Justice	488 - 489
	- <i>Ishan Mishra, Student, ICFAI University, Dehradun</i>	

SECTION (C) LEGAL ESSAY

RISE OF PEDOPHILES AMIDST THE CORONAVIRUS OUTBREAK

Section:	C
Category:	Legal Essay
Paper Code:	LE-BK-16
Page Number:	434 - 440
Date of Publication:	February 10, 2021
Citation:	Bulbul Kumari, Rise of Pedophiles amidst Coronavirus Outbreak, 1, AIJACLA, 434, 434-440, (2021).

DETAILS OF AUTHOR(S)

Bulbul Kumari

Student

Dharmashastra National Law University, Jabalpur

Email id: singhbulbul12112@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

During the lockdown period, imposed due to the outbreak of COVID-19, utilization of the internet and popularity of various social media platforms increased at a significant height. Along with it, children across the globe were forced to stay back at home due to the closure of the educational institutions and in certain cases were made to suffer inhuman legacies of sexual harassment, violence, etc. Due to the increased use of the internet in such a period, instances of child pornography were also found to have increased. This particular legal essay focuses on the issue of pedophiles in India amidst the COVID-19 pandemic.

KEYWORDS

Children, COVID-19, Lockdown, Pornographic Contents, and Paedophiles

INTRODUCTION

The whole world is fighting against the coronavirus pandemic. The scale and severity of the COVID-19 pandemic is rising day by day. Certain restrictions have been imposed on certain rights such as the imposition of quarantine or complete lockdown in the nation limiting the freedom of movement. The whole world is taking stringent steps to combat this

outbreak. People are directed to stay indoors at their homes to fight against the coronavirus.

The whole nation is at standstill due to the outbreak of COVID-19 and there is imposition of complete lockdown in the country to avert the spread of coronavirus. While a lot of facilities and services are at a virtual standstill, the rate of child sexual abuse has been on the rise. They are also exposing children to increased risk of violence- including maltreatment,

gender-based violence, and sexual exploitation.¹The complete lockdown of the nation to combat the outbreak of Coronavirus has resulted in an increase in online activities by millions of pedophiles, child rapists, and child pornography addicts. This has resulted in the internet being extremely unsafe for our children.

The Internet has become a tool for accessing pornographic contents which are harmful effects on society as they increase the incidents of sex crimes. The pervasive escalation of the virus has forced the children and the parents to spend maximum time on the internet. The India Child Protection Fund (ICPF) has found a steep rise in demand of searches like “child porn”, “sexy child” and “teen sex videos”.² Data from Pornhub also reveals that there has been an increase in the traffic by 95% between 24th and 26th March, 2020 as compared to their average traffic, pre-Coronavirus. The problem of child sexual abuse within society is an epidemic that virtually all children are at risk of abuse. International Criminal Police Organisation (Interpol) defines ‘Child Pornography’ as “means of depicting or promoting

sexual abuse of a child, including print and/or audio, centered on sex acts or genital organs of children.³

There has been a steep rise in demand for online Child Sexual Abuse Material (CSAM), which has made children more vulnerable to online pedophiles. As per the survey of the world vision, up to 85 million more girls and boys worldwide may be exposed to physical, sexual, or emotional violence over the three-month lockdown period.⁴ The pedophiles and child pornography addicts are building an emotional connection with the children and luring them and threatening them to perform sexual activities through photos and videos. They record and store this content to distribute it, and use it to extort the child to commit further abuse and exploitation.⁵

The demand for CSAM is higher in big cities like Kolkata, Siliguri, Howrah, Chandigarh, Guwahati, Indore, Bhubaneswar, and Chennai.⁶ The demand for generic child pornography content is higher in cities like Bhubaneswar and Chennai. It is found out that

¹ Joint Leaders' statement - Violence against children: A hidden crisis of the COVID-19 pandemic, World Health, (Sep. 2020, 28, 09:23 AM), <https://www.who.int/news-room/detail/08-04-2020-joint-leader-s-statement---violence-against-children-a-hidden-crisis-of-the-covid-19-pandemic>.

² Online search for child pornography escalates after lockdown in India, Deccan Herald, (Sep. 2020, 29, 05:34 PM), <https://www.deccanherald.com/national/online-search-for-child-pornography-escalates-after-lockdown-in-india-827602.html>.

³ Sexual Abuse of Children on the Internet: a new challenge for Interpol, UNESCO Digital Library, (Sep. 2020, 30, 03:45 PM), <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000114734>.

⁴ COVID-19 Aftershocks: A Perfect Storm, World Vision International, (Oct. 2020, 02, 07:25 PM), <https://www.wvi.org/publications/report/coronavirus-health-crisis/covid-19-aftershocks-perfect-storm>.

⁵ Child Sexual Abuse Material in India, Report on Demand for Child Pornography & Pilot Deterrence using Artificial Intelligence, India Child Protection Fund, (Oct. 2020, 02, 10:11 PM), https://7d53df5d-623a-479f-89b5-c88a0757a721.filesusr.com/ugd/aeb656_0247bfeadc04490b8e44e4fba71e3ad7.pdf.

⁶ Ibid.

the overall demand for child pornography is was an average of 5 million per month in 100 cities on the public web during December 2019, which is now rising.⁷ There has been a 200% spurt in demand for violent child abuse content since December 2019.⁸

LEGAL FRAMEWORK AND JUDICIAL APPROACH CONCERNING CHILD PORNOGRAPHY IN INDIA

The advancement in technology and the easy access to the internet across the country has complicated the process of keeping a check on increasing mal-practices which made it necessary to have zero tolerance in child pornography laws. This practice not only puts the children's life at risk but also violating the right to live with dignity which is guaranteed under Article 21 of the Constitution of India.

POSCO Act, 2012

The POCSO (Amendment) Act 2019, the most progressive law of the Indian government to protect all children who are under the age of 18 years, defines child pornography as any visual depiction of

⁷ Demand for child pornography in India spiked since lockdown: ICPF, Economics Times, (Oct. 2020, 04, 09:45 AM), <https://ciso.economictimes.indiatimes.com/news/demand-for-child-pornography-in-india-spiked-since-lockdown-icpf/75127959>.

⁸ In-built automated filtering only for child porn: MeitY's draft rules, The Economics Times, (Oct. 2020, 04, 07:25 PM), https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/tech/ites/in-built-automated-filtering-only-for-child-porn-meitys-draft-rules/articleshow/74091469.cms?utm_source=contentofinterest&utm_medium=text&utm_campaign=cppst.

sexually explicit conduct involving a child including photographs, video, digital, or computer-generated image indistinguishable from an actual child.⁹ The enlarged definition has helped to cover a wider aspect of a new trend of a variety of offenses under which an accused can be punished.

Information Technology Act, 2000

The IT Act, 2000 contains the provisions related to cyber pornography and specifically prohibited child pornography under Section 67B. The punishment for the same is prescribed under Section 67A and 67B of the IT Act. Punishment for the first conviction is imprisonment for a maximum of five years and a fine of ten lakh rupees and in the event of subsequent conviction with imprisonment of seven years and a fine of ten lakh rupees.

In the landmark case of *Jan Hit Manch & Ors. v. The Union of India*¹⁰, a PIL was filed to seek a blanket ban on pornographic websites under Section 67B of the IT Act.

Indian Penal Code, 1860

Under the Indian Penal Code (IPC), obscenity has been made a separate offense under Section 292, and pornography is considered as a part of it and so prohibits prohibition and transmission of obscene

⁹ The Protection of Children From Sexual Offences (Amendment) Act, 2019.

¹⁰ *Janhit Manch v. State of Maharashtra*, (2019) 2 SCC 505.

material. This also provided stringent measures to curb the crime where the punishment may extend to death in case of aggravated sexual assault.

In the case of *Kamlesh Vaswani vs. Union of India and others*¹¹, a writ petition was filed to block pornographic websites and to restrict both private and public access to them on the grounds of ‘obscenity’ under section 292, 293, and 294 of IPC.

INTERNATIONAL LEGAL FRAMEWORKS

The UN Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC)

This convention protects the children from any forms of sexual exploitation including the exploitation of children in pornographic acts. Article 6(1) of the UNCRC states that all children have the inherent right to survive and develop. The state must ensure maximum care, their development needs, protection needs, and social integration by adopting a child-friendly approach in the best interest of the children.

The United Nations Convention against Transnational Organized Crime (UNTOC)

Through various studies, it has been found out that child pornography is an organized crime. This United Nations Treaty is against all forms of organized crimes. This treaty aims to criminalize the organized crimes such as acts involving child sexual abuse.

¹¹ Kamlesh Vaswani v. Union of India, (2014) 6 SCC 705.

This shows that the protection and welfare of children is universally recognized as they hold the future of our country.

India has tied up with the US-based private non-profit organization National Centre for Missing and Exploited Children (NCMEC) which uses software to track child pornography content online to get the details like the IP address of the device used. Over 25,000 cases of suspected child pornography material were uploaded across social media in India in the last five months as per the report of NCMEC in the US with the National Crime Records Bureau.¹²

STEPS TAKEN TO COMBAT CHILD SEXUAL ABUSE

India is not an exception in this increasing trend of sexual violence in this pandemic and has been considered as the greatest source of more online child pornography as compared to any other country. Internet Service providers have been asked in the last few years to ban as many websites promoting child porn till the centralized mechanism is built in India to dynamically monitor websites/URLs containing online CSAM.

The Central Bureau of Investigation (CBI) has also set up an Online Child Sexual Abuse Exploitation

¹² US alert for India: 25,000 child porn cases uploaded in five months, The Indian Express, (Oct. 2020, 05, 10:00 AM), <https://indianexpress.com/article/india/child-pornography-india-ncmec-us-report-6238603/lite/>.

(OCSAE) Prevention and Investigation Unit at Delhi under its special Crime Zone to collect, collate and disseminate information regarding publication, transmission, creation, distribution of information relating to online child sexual abuse.

Many web portals are also there to lodge a complaint against child pornography and sexual abuse cases like cybercrime.gov.in launched by Home Ministry, CCPWC, and Operation Blackface in Maharashtra etc. However, many NGOs like RAHI Foundation, Amnesty International, Women Against Violence Europe (WAVE), etc. have taken tremendous steps to combat violence against women and children.

A Delhi-based NGO with the 'The Rakshin Project' initiating a free online session that will be open to prevent all forms of child sexual abuse and gender-based violence. Furthermore, an NGO Child Rights and You (CRY) also conducted a survey with Forum for Learning and Action with Innovation and Rigour (FLAIR) which revealed that 30% of the adolescents had a negative experience on the internet.

Many of the instances even goes unreported. The schools and colleges are physically at standstill. The classes are happening over various video conferencing apps such as 'Zoom'. This has put the children at high risk to become victims of child sexual abuse. In a recent case of *Harsh Chugh vs.*

*Union of India*¹³, the writ petition was filed in Supreme Court to deal with the issue of 'zoo bombing'. It means that when an unauthorized person or stranger joins a Zoom meeting/chat session and causes disorder by saying offensive things and even photo bombing the meeting by sharing pornographic and/or hate images. These incidents have caused great risk to the children.

In Re, (2018) 17 SCC 79¹⁴, the Supreme Court has imposed costs of Rs 1 lakh on each leading corporation such as Google, Whatsapp, Yahoo, and Microsoft who were failed to submit their stand on taking steps to prohibit the circulation of child porn videos. The Supreme Court with the Bench of CJI SA Bobde, AS Bopanna, and Hrishikesh Roy in response to the PIL filed by the BachpanBachaoAndolan for framing for the rescue and rehabilitation of the children amid the COVID-19 pandemic mulled over forming a committee to look into the issue.¹⁵

The bench asked if private establishments and employers can also be registered formally to protect the children from the onslaught of abuse and violence. This can help in restricting the employment

¹³ Harsh Chugh v. Union of India.

¹⁴ In Re, (2018) 17 SCC 79.

¹⁵ Supreme Court mulls forming Committee to check on the issue of Child Trafficking for Child Labour in private establishments, Bar and Bench, (Oct. 2020, 07, 11:45 AM), <https://www.barandbench.com/news/litigation/sc-mulls-forming-committee-check-on-child-trafficking-child-labour-private-establishments>.

of children at cheap labor in response to the deep agrarian crisis and economic conditions of the country.

THE WAY FORWARD

Due to the increasing rate of child pornography during the lockdown, there is a need to take immediate steps to stop the spread and proliferation of child pornography and for its complete elimination. The complete onus should be given to internet service providers (ISPs) by giving a code of conduct to remove all CSAM in any electronic form or containing sexually explicit acts.

Social media should also have stricter and watertight mechanisms for age verification to restrict the involvement of underage children who are more prone to be befriended by the influencer to perform sexual activities.

The parliamentary panel has also given its recommendation that the National Commission for Protection of Child Rights (NCPCR) should be given more responsibilities to include technology, cyber policing, and prosecution.¹⁶ A special cell should be created in all the states in the cyber dome to break the chain of child abusers who trade with obscene materials. A similar call has also been created in

¹⁶ Panel suggests steps to curb child porn, The Hindu, (Oct. 2020, 08, 12:25 PM), <https://www.thehindu.com/news/national/panel-suggests-steps-to-curb-child-porn/article30756641.ece/amp/>.

Kerala who uses encrypted apps such as telegram and gathered the IP address of around 150 people.¹⁷

The shift of classrooms to online mode has kept the student engaged with online resources more than before which has now emerged as a potential risk of online abuse. The online platform should be provided to the students where they can be given mental counseling regularly. Increasing the manpower that is having technical knowledge and is experts in internet pornography from the private sector can also help in close monitoring of online activities.

There has been an explosion of Internet usage and the number of internet users has exceeded 500 million and is likely to have reached 627 million in 2019 as predicted Kantar IMRB ICUBE report.¹⁸ We, therefore, need to have internet censorship as this explosion has opened the door to social evils to prevent the children from avail contents such as pornography. In the case of *State of U.P. v Lalai Singh Yadav*,¹⁹ the court ordered that between free speech and public order, the latter should be given

¹⁷ Kerala cops collect IP addresses of 150 people who downloaded child porn amid lockdown, The Indian Express, (Oct. 2020, 09, 01:05 PM), <https://www.newindianexpress.com/states/kerala/2020/apr/17/kerala-cops-collect-ip-addresses-of-150-people-who-downloaded-child-porn-amid-lockdown-2131516.amp>.

¹⁸ India's internet base crosses 500 million mark, driven by Rural India, Live Mint, (Oct. 2020, 11, 8:23 PM), <https://www.livemint.com/industry/telecom/internet-users-exceed-500-million-rural-india-driving-growth-report-1552300847307.html>.

¹⁹ State of U.P. v. Lalai Singh Yadav, (1977 AIR 202).

precedence. Complete restraint is impossible but an attempt should be made not to free it completely.

CONCLUSION

There is an alarming rise in the number of pedophiles and an increase in the number of child sexual abuse has put the children worldwide at extraordinary risk. In the year 2019, twitter took down 244,188 unique accounts for sharing child pornography, WhatsApp blocked 130,000 accounts and Instagram has removed 1.2 million child porn images.²⁰ Despite having stringent laws and taking such steps, the child sexual abuse is increasing. We must strive to start reporting such incidents so that cyber-crimes do not go unreported anymore.

²⁰ The dark web of child porn, India today, (Oct. 2020, 12, 08:10 PM), <https://www.indiatoday.in/amp/magazine/editor-s-note/story/20200302-from-the-editor-in-chief-1648214-2020-02-2>.